

Unexpected self-assembly of carbon dots during digital light processing 3D printing of vanillin Schiff-base resin

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ABSTRACT

Bio-based and recyclable composite thermosets were obtained through digital light processing (DLP) 3D printing by dispersing cellulose-derived carbon dots (CDs) in a photocurable vanillin Schiff-base resin. The exposure of CDs to DLP induced a partial reduction of the oxygen functionalities and a self-assembly of CDs into micrometric fibers embedded in the thermoset matrix. A comparison with the vanillin Schiff-base thermoset, illustrated lower transition temperature from the glassy to the rubbery state and inferior shape memory properties for the CD containing thermoset. This is ascribed to a lower crosslinking density due to the replacement of the covalent interactions of the thermosets with supramolecular interactions generated inside the microfibers and between the microfibers and the surrounding matrix. This can also explain the inferior mechanical rigidity of the composites with respect to the single component thermosets. However, the supramolecular interactions endow the composites with better mechanical and chemical recyclability with an almost complete preservation of the original mechanical properties.

1. Introduction

In order to meet the requirements of the circular economy, thermosets, highly crosslinked polymeric networks, need to be designed from bio-based resources and to show recyclability. Over the years, a wide range of natural molecules have been investigated as potential renewable resources for the synthesis of bio-based thermosets [1–5]. To reach the recyclability, the rethinking of the thermosets' chemical structure is a mandatory requirement and could be reached by exploiting the principles of the dynamic covalent chemistry (DCC). Among the DCCs, the Schiff-base reaction is acknowledged as a powerful family of reactions that can be successfully utilized under mild conditions often without the need of a catalyst. Due to the presence of an aldehyde function in its structure, vanillin, mainly extracted from lignin, has been investigated as a suitable building block for the realization of imine-containing Schiff-base thermosets [6–10]. In the frame of photopolymerizable resins, the methacrylation of vanillin-based monomers followed by their imination has also been reported as a route to thermosets with mechanical reprocessability [11–13] and chemical recyclability [11].

Very limited research was performed on the employment of vanillin Schiff-base resins for the development of composite thermosets. In these

works, graphene nanoplatelets and carbon fibers were reported as additives in vanillin-containing polyimine networks and the possibility to recover fillers after the deconstruction of the thermoset matrix was also documented. In this context, Lyu et al. reported the incorporation of commercial graphene nanoplatelets (GnPS) in vanillin-based polyimine thermosets; the 8% w/w concentration turns out to be sufficient to confer thermal conductivity to the nanocomposites [14]. Liu et al. developed a Schiff-base composite using vanillin, epoxidized soybean oil and 4-aminophenol for the matrix and a carbon fiber fabric for the obtainment of the thermoset composites [15]. Carbon fiber fabrics were also used for the production of fire-resistant thermosets by incorporating the fabric in a polyimine vanillin-terminated phosphazene matrix [16]. In all these cases, the degradability of the thermoset and the recovery of the filler in mild acidic conditions was documented. However, the synthesis of vanillin Schiff-base composites by means of photocuring processes was not investigated.

Concerning bio-based additives, carbon dots (CDs) demonstrate great potential due to the possibility to be added in the polymeric matrix through different methods, for example; by physical blending [17–19] which relies on the formation of secondary interactions between the CDs and the polymer; chemical grafting [20,21] reached i.e. through the chemical modification of the CDs and the establishment of covalent

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interactions with the polymeric chains of the matrix; or *in situ* growth [22,23], obtained by performing a single step procedure enabling to the contextual synthesis of CDs and of the polymeric matrix starting from a solution containing their precursors. The incorporation of CDs led to development of composite materials suitable for a wide range of applications [24–29]. In the frame of energy storage, CDs have been employed for the design of electrode materials, modification of separators and electrolyte additives of different battery systems [30]. The incorporation of CDs in conducting polymers has also demonstrated to promote motion of electrons and ions during the charge/discharge process, showing great potential for the development of advanced supercapacitors [31,32]. The chemical functionalities on the surface of CDs have been also exploited for the quantitative detection of chemical contaminants in water [33–35], by exploiting the alteration of electron, charge or energy transmission pathways occurring as a consequence of the interactions between the contaminant molecules and the CDs' functionalities [24]. In the medical field, the conjugation of graphene quantum dots with folate has shown to selectively target folate receptor-positive tumor cells, and enabled their detection [36]. Moreover, the absorption of properly functionalized graphene quantum dots on the DNA of cancer cells has led to DNA damage and suppression of cancer cell growth thanks to the establishment of π - π and electrostatic interactions [37]. Graphene quantum dots added to poly(ϵ -caprolactone) matrix have been applied to achieve biomimetic scaffolds which promote the nucleation of CaP crystals, thanks to their nanosize and presence of oxygen functionalities [38].

In the presented work, we developed bio-based resins by combining a vanillin Schiff-base photocurable monomer with CDs. We envisioned that the introduction of CDs could induce the establishment of additional secondary interactions inside the thermoset composite, which could have positive influence on the resulting properties in particular in terms of improved mechanical and chemical recyclability. Thermosets were obtained by subjecting the resin to the digital light processing (3D) printing. The resulting thermoset was fully characterized in terms of morphological, chemical, thermal and mechanical properties and compared with a vanillin Schiff-base thermoset without CDs. Finally, the influence of CD addition on the mechanical and chemical recyclability of the thermosets was also investigated.

2. Experimental part

2.1. Materials

Vanillin (V) (99%), ethylene carbonate (EC) (98%), potassium carbonate (K_2CO_3) ($\geq 99\%$), methacrylic anhydride (MAA) (94%), ethylenediamine (ED) ($\geq 99\%$), sodium sulfate ($\geq 99\%$), α -cellulose, sulfuric acid (H_2SO_4 ; 95–98%), nitric acid (70%; HNO_3), phenylbis(2,4,6-trimethylbenzoyl)phosphine oxide (BAPO) (97%), N,N-dimethylformamide (DMF) ($\geq 99\%$), and hydrochloric acid (HCl) (37%) were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich and used without any additional purification. 4-(dimethylamino)pyridine (DMAP) ($\geq 99.0\%$, Fluka), sodium bicarbonate ($\geq 99\%$, Merck), sodium hydroxide (NaOH) ($\geq 99\%$, Fisher Scientific), ethyl acetate (EtOAc) ($\geq 99\%$, VWR), dichloromethane (DCM) ($\geq 99\%$, Fisher Scientific), ethanol (EtOH) (99.8%, VWR), acetone ($\geq 99.5\%$, VWR) were all used as received.

2.2. Synthesis of Schiff-base resin

The Schiff-base resin was synthesized according to a triple step procedure consisting of a nucleophilic substitution reaction to obtain the extended vanillin (ExtV), the methacrylation of ExtV resulted in methacrylated extended vanillin (M-ExtV) and a Schiff-base reaction between M-ExtV and ED produced the Schiff-base resin (SB).

ExtV was synthesized according to the previous reported procedure [11]. 10.00 g of V (65.72 mmol), 6.38 g of EC (72.45 mmol) and 11.00 g of K_2CO_3 (79.59 mmol) were added to a 250 mL round-bottom flask and

solubilized in 100 mL of DMF under magnetic stirring. The reaction was carried out at 110 °C for 12 h under reflux in a N_2 atmosphere. After the verification of the completion of the reaction with TLC plate, the mixture was cooled down to room temperature, diluted in distilled water (150 mL) and then poured in EtOAc (150 mL). The aqueous phase was separated and extracted with EtOAc (2×100 mL). The organic phases were mixed, washed with water (2×200 mL), dried over sodium sulfate, concentrated under reduced pressure and further dried in vacuum oven at 60 °C for 12 h, yielding ExtV (white powder, 70% yield).

The methacrylation of ExtV was performed by slightly modifying the previous protocol [11]. ExtV (10.00 g, 51.02 mmol), MAA (8.58 g, 55.66 mmol) and DMAP (38.00 mg, 0.32 mmol) were mixed together in a 100 mL round-bottom flask, under reflux and N_2 flow. The reaction was performed at 60 °C for 24 h, the product was diluted with DCM (300 mL) and consequentially washed with saturated aqueous solution of sodium bicarbonate (2×300 mL), 0.5 M NaOH (2×300 mL), 1 M NaOH (2×300 mL) and distilled water (150 mL). The organic phase was dried over sodium sulfate, concentrated at reduced pressure and dried under vacuum at 30 °C for two days, yielding M-ExtV (pale yellowish powder, 85% yield).

SB was obtained through the imination of M-ExtV with ED by slight modification of previously reported procedure. M-ExtV (12.00 g, 45.40 mmol), and ED (1.37 g, 22.74 mmol) in 150 mL of DCM were added to a 150 mL round-bottom flask and kept under stirring at room temperature for 5 h. The collected reaction mixtures were washed according to the procedure described for the methacrylation reaction, yielding SB (white powder, 82% yield). SB 1H NMR (400.13 MHz, DMSO- d_6): δ ppm 8.25 (s, 2H, -HCN-), 7.35 (d, 2H, Ar), 7.20–7.17 (m, 2H, Ar), 7.04 (d, 2H, Ar), 6.02 (s, 2H, -C=CH₂), 5.69 (t, 2H, -C=CH₂), 4.46–4.39 (m, 4H, -OCH₂CH₂OH), 4.39–4.26 (m, 4H, -OCH₂CH₂OH), 3.82 (s, 4H, -NCH₂CH₂N-), 3.78 (s, 6H, -OCH₃), 1.87 (s, 6H, -C-CH₃).

2.3. Synthesis of cellulose-derived carbon dots

The synthesis of carbon dots (CDs) was performed by means of a microwave-assisted hydrothermal carbonization with some modifications with respect to previously published works [19,39,40]. 2 g of α -cellulose and 20 mL of 0.1 g/mL H_2SO_4 were added to a Teflon vessel. Three vessels were run at the same time. Carbonization was performed in a Milestone flexiWAVE MA186-001 microwave oven by increasing the temperature to 220 °C with a ramp time of 20 min and keeping the vessels at this temperature for 2 h under magnetic stirring. The temperature was monitored with a probe inside one of the vessels. The resulting black carbon spheres (CSs) were filtered, washed with water, and dried in a vacuum oven for 24 h. Afterwards, 250 mg of CSs were added to 25 mL of 70% HNO_3 in a round-bottom flask and left to sonicate for 1 h at 45 °C. The reaction mixture was then refluxed in an oil bath at 90 °C for 30 min, after which it was poured into 200 mL of H_2O ; the acidic water was then neutralized through 24 h dialysis against distilled water. The final product was vacuum-dried and CDs with a reddish color were obtained.

2.4. General procedure for the digital light processing 3D printing of the resins

After their synthesis, SB and CDs were employed for the production of the resins for the printing. SB resin was obtained by dissolving the Schiff-base monomer in DCM with a concentration of 70% w/v; an additional step consisting of addition of CDs with a concentration of 1% w/w was performed for the obtainment of the SB + CD resins. In both cases, 5% w/w BAPO was added to the mixture.

The resulting thermosets, labeled XSB and XSB + CD, were produced using a digital light processing (DLP) 3D printer (Asiga MAX X27 UV) with a 385 nm light source. Build files and printing parameters were processed using the Asiga Composer software. Based on the resulting working curves, SB and SB + CD resin solutions were printed using

exposure times for the curing of each layer of 121 s and 170 s, respectively. All composites had a layer thicknesses of 0.05 mm and the light intensity was set to 28.8 mW/cm². Residual uncured resin was removed from the surfaces of the prints by washing them in two distinct DCM baths. The post-curing of the prints was performed in a 385 nm UV chamber (Asiga Flash) for 6 min (3 min for each side). The 3D printed specimens were then dried in vacuum oven at 30 °C until a constant weight was reached.

2.5. Mechanical and chemical recycling

The mechanical recycling of XSB and XSB + CD was performed by cutting the printed films (32 × 20 × 1 mm) in small pieces, after which they were transferred in a square-shaped mold and hot-pressed at 150 °C for 10 min under 2 MPa. The chemical recycling of XSB was performed according to the procedure reported in Ref. [11] with few modifications. Briefly, 0.750 g of XSB were solubilized in 6 mL of ED for 4 h at 60 °C. The resulting product was precipitated in water, subjected to vacuum filtration and dried under vacuum at 50 °C for 72 h. Afterwards, 0.300 g of the collected product 0.100 mg of fresh M-ExtV and 0.010 g of BAPO were mixed inside a round-bottom flask with a magnetic stir. The powder was then poured in a square-shaped mold (25 × 25 × 0.5 mm) and hot-pressed at 120 °C for 10 min under 2 MPa. The resulting film was UV cured on both the sides for 6 min (3 min for each side). The chemical recycling of XSB + CD was carried out with the same procedure used for XSB, with an additional step consisting in adding 1% w/w fresh CDs to the round-bottom flask containing M-ExtV and BAPO.

2.6. Characterizations

The ¹H NMR of SB was performed on an Avance 400 (Bruker, U.S.A.) spectrometer (400 MHz). Deuterium dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) was used as the solvent and also utilized as the internal standard for calibrating the chemical shift. The surface and cross-sectional morphologies of XSB and XSB + CD, as well as the morphology of CDs, were investigated by means of scanning electron microscopy (SEM, Hitachi S-4800). The samples were attached on an aluminum stub using carbon tape and sputter coated with chromium (Cr) for 5 min. All SEM micrographs were taken with an acceleration voltage of 1 kV. The chemical structures of SB, CSs, CDs, XSB and XSB + CD were analyzed via a PerkinElmer Spectrum 2000 Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) spectrometer (Norwalk, CT) equipped with an attenuated total reflectance (ATR) sampling accessory. All spectra were recorded in the wavenumber range of 4000–600 cm⁻¹ using 16 scans at a resolution of 4 cm⁻¹. Rheological tests were performed by means of rheometer DHR-2 (TA instrument) with disposable smooth aluminum parallel plates (20 mm diameter). The rheometer was coupled with UV light emitting diode arrays (365 nm, 900 mW/cm²). The resin was set down on a quartz plate (20 mm diameter). After setting the gap at 500 μm, the light source was turned on with a delay of 60 s with respect to the beginning of the

experiment. Variations in the storage modulus were recorded as a function of time at a frequency of 1 Hz and a constant applied strain of 0.1%.

Thermogravimetry analysis (TGA) of both thermosets was performed by a TGA/SDTA851e (METTLER TOLEDO, U.S.A.). Samples weighting around 10 mg, were inserted in 70 μL ceramic crucibles and subjected to a heating scan from 30 °C to 600 °C with a heating rate of 10 °C/min and under a 50 mL/min nitrogen flow.

Dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA) of the thermosets was performed by using a TA Instruments Q800 in tension film mode. The experiments, in a multifrequency strain mode, were performed with a force track of 125% at a frequency of 1.0 Hz. The deflection amplitude of oscillation and Poisson's ratio were set at 15 μm and 0.44, respectively. The samples were equilibrated at 25 °C for 5 min and tested from 35 °C to 180 °C at 1 Hz with an amplitude oscillation of 15 μm and at a 3 °C/min heating rate. The glass transition temperature (*T_g*) was considered as the maximum of the tan δ curve. The same instrument was employed to investigate the stress relaxation properties of the thermosets at 100 °C, 140 °C, 180 °C and 220 °C. The thermosets were first heated to the desired temperature and equilibrated for 5 min; after that, a constant 1% strain was applied to the thermosets, and the relaxation modulus and stress were recorded over time.

Tensile tests were performed on 3D printed bars (26 × 1.53 × 0.75 mm) and on mechanically and chemically recycled specimens using an Instron 5944 equipped with a 500 N load cell. Sample were conditioned in a controlled environment with a temperature of 22 °C and 40% relative humidity for 2 days before testing.

3. Results and discussion

Bio-based Schiff-base resins (SB and SB + CD) were successfully derived from vanillin without and with CDs. CDs were obtained by oxidation of CS produced through hydrothermal carbonization of cellulose. The scheme for the whole process to produce cured 3D printed thermosets XSB (thermoset) and XSB + CD (composite) is reported in Fig. 1. The synthesis of the Schiff-base monomer (SB) through the three-step reaction described in the experimental part was confirmed by ¹H NMR (Fig. S1). The addition of oxidized CDs was fundamental to obtain composite thermosets, XSB + CD. The particles ensured good dispersion in DCM and prevented the formation of aggregates.

3.1. DLP of the resins and investigation of the morphology of thermosets and composites

Fig. 2 reports the comparison between the printed thermoset and composite and the respective computer assisted models. The comparison of the printed honeycombs and stars with the computer models shows that the composite models could be printed with higher resolution, as observable by the lack of over-cured areas in the cells of the honeycomb print (compare Fig. 2c with Fig. 2b) together with the identification of

Fig. 1. Scheme of the processes for the obtainment of XSB and XSB + CD.

sharper edges and “eyes” in the star print (compare Fig. 2f with Fig. 2e).

For the DLP process, the presence of a solvent in the resins' formulation was necessary due to the solid nature of SB. The solvent enabled the solubilization of the resin and its photopolymerization to form the thermosets and composites, but on the other side the volatility of the solvent also affected the maximum printing time and, therefore, the maximum thickness of the prints. Indeed, for printing time longer than 1.5 h significant changes in the resin properties took place due to initiated solidification. Considering this aspect, the maximum printing time was not exceeded and the process was always performed at room temperature to reduce the solvent evaporation.

According to the state of the art in stereolithography [41,42], ceramic fillers dispersed in the resins generally act as light scattering agents, leading to non-uniform curing and a decrease in the efficiency of the process. Differently from these studies, the improvement of the printing resolution observed in the presence of CDs, suggest their role as light absorbers limiting the light penetration depth through the otherwise pale yellow-transparent SB resin solution, thereby reducing the undesired curing of additional layers. This result is further supported by the working curves reported in Fig. S2, documenting a lower penetration depth of the UV radiation in the SB + CD resin with respect to SB. This agrees with previous works reporting the positive effect of the addition of methacrylated wood flour or lignin nanoparticles as fillers on the resolution of DLP objects [43,44].

A flat and homogenous morphology without any major surface or cross-section features was illustrated in the SEM images of XSB (Fig. 3b and c). Conversely, XSB + CD turned out to be endowed with an interesting and surprising morphology, characterized by the presence of microfibers (mean diameter around 15 μm) clearly embedded in the XSB matrix (Fig. 3d, e, 3f). As observable, the main characteristic morphology of CDs showed spherical shape with a mean diameter around 1 μm (Fig. 3a). This morphology was not recognizable in the composite, suggesting a self-assembly of the CDs to form continuous and homogenous fibers perfectly integrated in the thermoset architecture.

In order to get insights on the causes leading to the formation of these microfibers, an approach based on the separation of the effect was

carried out. It consisted of investigating, by means of SEM, the morphology of the single components of the thermosets before and after the UV exposure. As a first step, the morphology of as produced CDs dispersed in DCM in the presence of the photoinitiator before and after the UV exposure, performed for 6 min with the UV lamp, was investigated. While the morphology of CDs not subjected to the UV curing (Fig. 4a) turned out to be quite similar to the one of the as produced CDs (Fig. 3a), the formation of bidimensional foil-like structures with mean dimensions around few micrometers was detected after the UV treatment (Fig. 4d). The analysis performed by comparing the morphologies of the uncured SB dissolved in DCM in presence of BAPO and of the resulting thermosets obtained after 6 min of UV curing (3 min/side) clearly highlighted the transition from the crystalline morphology typical of SB monomer (Fig. 4b) to the homogenous and amorphous morphology of XSB (Fig. 4e); although, at higher magnifications, the presence of a certain roughness and sub-micrometric features was observed (inset Fig. 4e). Finally, the morphology of the SB + CD resin solution was investigated before and after the UV exposure. While no relevant features were observed for the uncured solution (Fig. 4c), fibers with diameters spanning from 1 μm to 10 μm emerging from the thermoset matrix were present in the composites (Fig. 4f and inset).

This clearly highlights the relevant role of the UV light on the self-assembly of CDs, which seems to occur independently of the presence of the resin (Fig. 4d); however, only in the presence of the polymeric matrix, fiber-like structures were observed (Fig. 4f). In agreement with previous works, this result can be explained by assuming that a partial reduction of CDs takes place under the UV light [45,46], with a consequent establishment of attractive electrostatic, van der Waals and π - π stacking interactions driving the self-assembly of CDs into thick CD-based fibers [47,48].

The hypothesis on the establishment of non-covalent interactions among the CDs and between the CDs and the thermoset matrix also finds confirmation from previous studies on the self-assembly phenomena of aromatic polymers. Huang et al. demonstrated that the spontaneous multiscale self-assembly of aromatic amide molecules was driven by strong intermolecular interactions such as hydrogen bonding and

Fig. 2. Digital light processing 3D printed honeycombs and stars produced from (b, e) SB and (c, f) SB + CD. Computer assisted model of (a) honeycomb and (d) star.

Fig. 3. SEM images of (a) CDs, (b, c) XSB and (d, e, f) XSB + CD; (b, d) surface and (c, e, f) cross-section.

electrostatic forces leading to the aggregation of the molecules into stable clusters, which further stack into robust columns, able to reach micrometric diameters and forming, thereby, microfibers [49]. Baraman et al. documented that also hydrophobic interactions, taking place among highly aromatic structures such as perylene diimide units, were effective in inducing self-assembly phenomenon explained by π -stacking and leading to the formation of micrometric fibers [50]. Furthermore, the authors also reported that the disassembly of the self-formed fibers was possible upon reduction. In the context of the self-assembly driven

by hydrophobic interactions, Goel et al. reported the potential of segmented poly(phenylene vinylene)s, characterized by π -cores with flexible methylene chains, to undergo aromatic π -stack interaction with the resulting formation of bundles of helical assemblies [51].

The formation of two dimensional structures in the plain UV lamp cured CD solution confirms the generation of favorable interactions between the CDs under UV light; however, the lack of well-defined fibers and the low number of fibers in the UV lamp cured XSB + CD can be explained considering the employed conditions. Indeed, for the UV lamp

Fig. 4. SEM images of (a) CD + BAPO in DCM, (b) SB resin solution and (c) SB + CD resin solution not subjected to UV exposure; (d) CD + BAPO in DCM, (e) SB resin solution and (f) SB + CD resin solution after being subjected to the UV lamp. (g–i) SEM images of vanillin + CD + BAPO in DCM after UV exposure.

curing, the resin solution was poured in a mold and subjected to the UV light for an arbitrary curing time, while in the DLP each layer of the resulting thermoset is singly cured for a predetermined time period selected for the achievement of more complete photopolymerization of the monomer. Since the UV light is not able to penetrate through the whole thickness of the film, it is probable that in the case of UV lamp exposure once the surface layer is photopolymerized, the curing of the underneath layers might not occur to completion, leading to non-uniform reduction of the CDs in the underneath layers.

In order to confirm this hypothesis, a final test was therefore performed by subjecting a 70% w/v solution of non-methacrylated vanillin in DCM containing CDs (1% w/w) and BAPO (5% w/w) to the UV lamp for 60 s. As expected, no solid thermosets were obtained at the end of the process due to the absence of photosensitive groups in vanillin. A few drops of the UV exposed solution were then dried and subjected to SEM analysis. As observable in Fig. 4g, h and 4i, a high number of solid and regular fibers, morphologically similar to those of the composite thermoset, were obtained. The fibers appear to be surrounded by the vanillin crystalline-like matrix and some very clear interactions between them and the surrounding matrix can be detected (i.e. inset of Fig. 4i). In tune with our hypothesis, the non-solidification of the vanillin solution under the UV light allows the radiation to penetrate through the solution leading to a more uniform reduction of CDs and, therefore, to fiber formation.

3.2. Characterizations of the thermosets and composites

The photopolymerization of SB and SB + CD during printing was confirmed by ATR-FTIR spectroscopy (Fig. 5), which clearly documented the differences in the spectra of the thermosets with respect to the spectrum of the monomer resins. In order to study the occurrence of

the curing, the spectrum of MAA was also considered. In particular, the success of the curing was confirmed by the decrease of the intensity of the peaks of $\text{C}=\text{C}$ -bending vibrations at 945 cm^{-1} and 640 cm^{-1} , assigned to the wagging and twisting of $=\text{CH}_2$ functions introduced with the methacrylation [13,52], and by the modification of the peaks in the regions $896\text{--}880\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $809\text{--}800\text{ cm}^{-1}$ ($=\text{CH}_2$ twisting [52]). Moreover, important changes in the spectra are also observed in the region $1322\text{--}985\text{ cm}^{-1}$. The printing did not affect the Schiff-base linkages, as the absorption bands of imine bond (at 1639 cm^{-1}) were still present after the photopolymerization, while the aldehyde characteristic peak (at 1675 cm^{-1}), typical of the MExt-V, was undetectable. As observable, the intense broad band of the hydroxyl functions characteristic of CDs turned out to be barely detectable in XSB + CD. This could be explained by the low concentration and formation of the self-assembled fiber structures.

The photopolymerization process of the two resins was monitored through the real-time FTIR spectroscopy focusing in the wavenumber range $950\text{--}833\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (Fig. 6a and b). Although the UV curing approach implemented during this measurement cannot be directly compared with the layer-by-layer photopolymerization of the DLP, also due to the different employed irradiation wavelength (365 nm for the real-time FTIR analysis vs 385 nm for DLP); the real-time FTIR documented the occurrence of the photopolymerization as observable from the modification of the band in the wavenumber region $896\text{--}880\text{ cm}^{-1}$. Moreover, the curing behavior of the SB + CD resin was very similar initially and 1 week after the preparation (Fig. S3), suggesting that the stability of the resin over time is good.

However, this analysis did not highlight significant differences in terms of curing kinetic between the two resins; therefore, photo-rheology was also performed to further investigate their photo-reactivity (Fig. 6c and d). The storage moduli were monitored during

Fig. 5. ATR-FTIR spectra of XSB, XSB + CD, SB, CDs and MAA in the wavenumber region (a) $4000\text{--}600\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and (b) $2000\text{--}600\text{ cm}^{-1}$. The symbol “diamond” indicates the hydroxyl functions; the symbol “triangle” indicates $\text{C}=\text{C}$ -bending vibrations; the symbol “star” indicates the Schiff-base linkages.

Fig. 6. Real-time FTIR recorded during the UV exposure of (a) SB and (b) SB + CD in the wavenumber region $950\text{--}833\text{ cm}^{-1}$. Photo-rheology of (c) SB and (d) SB + CD reporting the storage modulus as a function of the curing time.

the UV-curing process and, once the light was turned on at $t = 60\text{ s}$, their variations were recorded over time. In agreement with previous works [44,53], SB turned out to be much more photo-reactive than SB + CD. Indeed, while for SB the curing starts immediately after the turning on of the UV light; around 110 s were needed to SB + CD to initiate the photopolymerization. This result further confirms the light-absorbing action of CDs causing a delay in the photo-curing. Finally, the low value of the plateau storage modulus of SB + CD ($0.34 \pm 0.03\text{ kPa}$) suggests a lower density of covalent linkages in the composite with respect to XSB (storage modulus of $217 \pm 21\text{ kPa}$). This result agrees with the low penetration depth of the UV light through the CDs-containing resin documented by the working curves and confirms the lower curing degree of this resin with respect to SB when subjected to UV plain lamp.

The thermogravimetry analysis documented good heat resistance for both the thermoset and the composite with an onset of degradation ($T_{\text{deg}5\%}$) at $308 \pm 3\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $303 \pm 1\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ for XSB and XSB + CD, respectively. The thermoset and the composite showed similar maximum degradation temperatures ($T_{\text{deg max}}$) above $400\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ as well as a remaining mass at $600\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, likely due to the low concentration of CDs in the SB + CD resin solution (Fig. 7a and Table 1).

From the DMA tests in multifrequency strain mode (Fig. 7b and c, Table 1), both the thermoset and the composite turned out to show a high T_g ($91 \pm 2\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ for XSB and $85 \pm 4\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ for XSB + CD) and a characteristic vitrimer-like behavior. This is documented by the maintenance of a stable rubbery plateau also at temperature $90\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ – $100\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ above the T_g , indicating the preservation of the crosslinking density even at high temperatures. Interestingly, for XSB + CD the transition from the glassy

Fig. 7. (a) TGA curves of XSB (black) and XSB + CD (red). (b) Storage modulus and (d) Tan δ curves as a function of temperature obtained from DMA analysis of XSB (black) and XSB + CD (red). Normalized stress relaxation modulus for (d) XSB and (e) XSB + CD as a function of time at different temperatures. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Table 1

Thermal properties and gel content in DCM for XSB and XSB + CD.

Sample	T_g DMA (°C)	$T_{deg5\%}$ (°C)	$T_{deg max}$ (°C)	Residue (w/w%)	Gel content in DCM (w/w%)
XSB	91 ± 2	308 ± 3	414 ± 5	26 ± 2	87 ± 3
XSB + CD	85 ± 4	303 ± 1	415 ± 2	30 ± 3	91 ± 3

state to the rubbery plateau occurs at slightly lower temperatures than for XSB, probably due to a lower crosslinking density in the composite caused by the presence of CDs that both absorb light and do not participate in the photopolymerization reaction, as also confirmed by the photo-rheology measurements. This is expected to lead to an overall reduction in the density of covalent bonds and crosslinking degree. Nonetheless, the storage modulus of XSB + CD in the rubbery plateau is higher than the one registered for XSB, suggesting that the CD derived fibers had a reinforcing effect in the resulting thermoset at temperatures higher than T_g [54].

Stress relaxation measurements performed at different temperatures in the range from 100 °C to 220 °C on the thermoset and composite, highlighted significant differences in their capability to release the applied stress (Fig. 7d and e). Indeed, at 100 °C XSB + CD was not able to release the applied stress, differently from XSB for which a 37% stress relaxation modulus reduction was reached in around 4 min. For higher temperatures, the stress release over time was observed for both the thermoset and the composite with a generally shorter relaxation time for XSB. The results highlight the effective occurrence of imine exchange reactions for both XSB and XSB + CD at temperature of 140 °C or higher; on the other hand, they clearly documented the role of the CD originating fibers in hampering or delaying the activation of the metathesis pathway in the composite, confirming the incorporation of these structures in the thermoset matrix. Finally, from the comparison of the curves at different temperatures obtained for the same thermoset, the curves at 220 °C showed a different trend. After reaching the 37% reduction of the storage modulus, the normalized stress relaxation modulus decreased more slowly with respect to the curves obtained at lower temperatures, also reaching a plateau in a shorter time. This trend can be ascribed to a

completion of the curing taking place during the DMA measurements at such high temperature [55,56].

The same temperatures tested for the stress relaxation measurements were selected to study the malleability properties of both the thermoset and the composite. For the assessment of shape-memory properties, rectangular printed samples (26.00 × 1.53 × 0.75 mm) of XSB and XSB + CD were heated at a temperature higher than the T_g , bended and immediately cooled down to RT in order to block the conferred temporary shape. Afterwards, the prints were heated again at the desired temperature and the modification of the shape was recorded over time. Following this procedure, rectangular printed samples were subjected to 4 shape-memory cycles, where different temperatures were employed for the recovery of the original shape. An additional test was performed on honeycomb prints. In this case the temperature and the time to assess the recovery of the original geometry were fixed at 180 °C and 40 s, respectively.

As observable from Fig. 8a and b, the rectangular print of XSB was always able to recover the original shape in around 5–10 s independently of the employed temperature; similar to this, the honeycomb print returned to the non-bended shape after 40 s at 180 °C. Conversely, with the increasing number of heating cycles, the rectangular prints of XSB + CD were not able to fully recover the original geometry. Furthermore, the XSB + CD honeycomb still partially preserved the temporary shape after 40 s at 180 °C.

The results confirmed the efficacy of the crosslinks in XSB in returning the network to the original permanent shape upon heating above T_g . It is also interesting to notice that at the selected temperatures, the activation of the crosslinks occurs faster than the activation of the imine metathesis pathway (Fig. 7d); indeed, considering the

Fig. 8. (a) Shape memory behavior of rectangular printed samples of XSB and XSB + CD as a function of time at different temperatures. (b) Reversibility of the passage from the temporary shape to the initial shape for XSB and XSB + CD when heated at 180 °C for 40 s.

temperature range from 140 °C to 220 °C, only 10 s are needed for the shape recovery, while almost 60 s are necessary for the relaxation of the stress. This difference in the activation times confers malleability to the XSB prints, enabling the recovery of the permanent shape before the dynamic bond exchange with a consequent readjustment of the network takes place. These results are different from what we observed in our previous work in which XSB thermosets were obtained by curing the resin solution with UV lamp for 10 min instead of production of specimens by DLP [11]. In that case, the samples failed to recover the original shape when subjected to the third heating above the T_g , due to remodeling of the molecular structure by the activation of the imine pathway with the repeated heating cycles [57]. This indicates superior efficacy of the layer-by-layer curing during DLP 3D printing, which likely induces a higher crosslinking density with a consequent improvement of the thermo-sensitive malleability properties.

The unsuccess of the rectangular printed samples of XSB + CD to completely recover the original shape after the second heating cycle and the preservation of bended shape after 40 s at 180 °C is probably not caused by the activation of the imine metathesis pathways, but rather explained by the reduction of the oxygen functionalities in CDs during exposure to high temperatures with a consequent influence on network properties. Indeed, as shown in Fig. S4, a relevant reduction of the intensity and a modification of the –OH band was registered upon heating the as produced CDs at 180 °C for few minutes. Another possible explanation could be the lower number of crosslinks in XSB + CD with respect to the XSB thermoset due to the influence of light absorbing CDs that do not participate in the photopolymerization reaction and are not part of the covalent network.

The gel content measurements, performed by immersing XSB and XSB + CD (Table 1 and Table S1) in different common solvents for 72 h, documented that the samples preserved almost completely their original weight and no relevant differences could be noticed between the two thermosets, independent of the employed solvent. Moreover, the solvent resistance of XSB + CD in DCM turned out to be slightly higher than that of XSB. Therefore, although the presence of CDs can lead to a lower crosslinking density in the composites with respect to XSB, this does not affect the resulting solvent resistant properties. Interestingly, both materials also showed good stability in water. Indeed, as shown in Fig. S5, no relevant modifications of the ATR-FTIR spectra were registered, except for opening of few imine linkages with the consequential reformation of aldehyde functions. The result is ascribed to the

hydrophobicity of the materials with high density of aromatic functions in their structures.

3.3. Mechanical and chemical recycling

The comparison of mechanical properties of XSB and XSB + CD in Table 2, shows that both materials are rigid, with XSB showing a stiffer behavior (elastic modulus around 1 GPa and a stress at break around 51 MPa). These values are significantly higher than those obtained after photocuring of SB with the plain UV lamp (elastic modulus around 379 MPa and stress at break around 17 MPa) [11]. This shows the superior efficiency of the layer-by-layer curing during the DLP process.

The presence of the microfibers in the printed thermoset architecture seems to reduce the hardness. This phenomenon could be ascribed to a lower crosslink density in the composite; indeed, in XSB + CD part of the resin is replaced by the microfibers forming only secondary interactions with the thermoset. This together with light absorbing property of CDs is expected to cause an overall reduction in the number of covalent crosslinks, which are the main contributors to the network rigidity, in agreement with the photo-rheology studies. An additional explanation of the observed hardness reduction might be found in a possible displacement of the graphitic structures inside the microfibers [58]. When the materials were subjected to thermal reprocessing and chemical recycling, a change in the resulting mechanical properties was registered, as shown in Table 2 and in Fig. 9a and b. While quite significant deterioration was registered for XSB, which switched from being stiff to brittle with low values of elastic moduli; the mechanical properties were quite well preserved for XSB + CD after the thermal reprocessing and chemical recycling.

Table 2

Mechanical properties of DLP printed and mechanically and chemically recycled thermosets and composites.

Sample	Elongation at break [%]	Stress at break [MPa]	Elastic modulus [MPa]
XSB	8.0 ± 0.6	51.2 ± 10.2	1020 ± 140
XSB mech rec	5.2 ± 0.8	16.7 ± 2.9	714 ± 60
XSB chem rec	3.2 ± 1.4	6.7 ± 3.5	334 ± 75
XSB + CD	8.5 ± 1.2	22.4 ± 1.4	867 ± 17
XSB + CD mech rec	6.6 ± 0.5	21.7 ± 1.5	739 ± 62
XSB + CD chem rec	4.4 ± 0.6	15.2 ± 1.1	646 ± 26

Fig. 9. Characterizations of DLP 3D printed and reprocessed thermosets. (a) Stress-strain curves of XSB, mechanically recycled XSB and chemically recycled XSB; (b) Stress-strain curves of XSB + CD, (red) mechanically recycled XSB + CD and chemically recycled XSB + CD. (c) ATR-FTIR of XSB, mechanically recycled XSB and chemically recycled XSB; (d) ATR-FTIR of XSB + CD, mechanically recycled XSB + CD and chemically recycled XSB + CD. The symbol “star” indicates the peak of the aldehyde functions; the symbol “triangle” indicates the peak of $-C=C-$ bending vibrations. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

The ATR-FTIR analysis performed on the mechanically recycled samples (Fig. 9c and d) highlighted very similar spectra for XSB and XSB + CD reprocessed samples; indeed, in both cases the appearance of the peak of the aldehyde functions, suggesting the opening of some Schiff-base linkages, and a modification of the peaks ascribed to $-C=C-$, suggesting a possible completion of $C=C$ curing, was registered. Furthermore, it is possible that the cutting of the original thermosets in small pieces could contribute to the decrease of the mechanical properties [12]. This hypothesis is also confirmed by the results obtained after a second mechanical recycling. Indeed, the further decrease of the Young's modulus (Fig. S6a and Table S2) clearly demonstrates the deterioration of the network's structure and the loss of the original rigidity. In this context, the positive and promising results obtained for the recycled XSB + CD thermosets might be explained by assuming the establishment of secondary interactions between the CD fillers and the polymeric matrix, leading to a greater preservation of the mechanical properties during the reprocessing. These interactions are also preserved after the second mechanical recycling, as supported by the relatively unchanged elastic modulus (Fig. S6b and Table S2). At the same time the continuous reduction of the stress and strain at break with the increasing number of reprocessing cycles suggests that a modification of the network structure takes place also in the composites. This could be explained by a decrease of the density of supramolecular interactions

inside the network or to the damage of covalent bonds not restored during the hot-press step.

XSB chemically recycled samples showed significantly lower mechanical properties compared with their mechanically recycled counterpart. This difference can be explained by considering the change in the resin composition during the multi-step process employed for the chemical recycling, described in the experimental section and schematized in Fig. S7. In particular, since the original monomer cannot be recovered due to the establishment of irreversible covalent bonds during the photopolymerization, the imine transimination pathway was induced by solubilizing the thermoset in an excess of ED, as confirmed by the 1H NMR spectra in Fig. S8. This leads to recovery of oligomers with amine-end groups [11], and need to add virgin MExt-V to induce the Schiff base reaction in the solid-state through hot-pressing. Finally, to complete the curing of the vinyl functions of MExt-V the materials were subjected to the UV lamp. However, as shown in Fig. S9, this last step did not induce any significant change in the spectrum of the thermoset, except for a slight reduction of the intensity of the peaks at 946 cm^{-1} and 860 cm^{-1} with respect to the adjacent peak at 916 cm^{-1} , suggesting that the curing of the MExt-V mainly occurred already during the hot-press step, and was then completed during the UV exposure. The deterioration of the mechanical properties might therefore derive from the change in resin composition, presence of unreacted amine

end-groups and a damage of other covalent bonds which cannot be re-generated during the recycling procedure. The better chemical recyclability of XSB + CD can be ascribed also in this case to the establishment of secondary interactions between the thermoset and the filler and also to the addition of new CDs during the recycling process.

With respect to the results reported in a recent work on the DLP of Schiff-base vanillin resins obtained from methacrylated or acrylated vanillin coupled with Jeffamine diamines and triamines, both, the thermoset and composite turned out to better preserve their original shape under applied stress, showing significantly higher values of elastic modulus and lower deformation at break [12]. Concerning the recovery of the properties after the mechanical reprocessing, the presence of CDs in the printed thermoset and the interactions that they establish with the surrounding matrix significantly improved the preservation of the mechanical properties after the recycling leading to approximately 85% recovery of the elastic modulus, which is close to 90%, the highest value reported in Ref. [12]. With respect to the chemically recycled XSB thermosets produced previously by photocuring of the resin with the UV lamp [11], the chemically recycled XSB thermosets presented in this work showed very similar mechanical properties, while a clear improvement was registered in the presence of CDs, further supporting the key role of the secondary interactions in the preservation of the original mechanical properties.

The investigation of the morphology of mechanically and chemically recycled XSB + CD highlighted the absence of the previously observed fibers in the mechanically recycled samples (Fig. 10a), while only few micrometer long fibers were still detectable after the chemical recycling (Fig. 10d and e). The difference between the two samples can be ascribed to the specific procedures employed for the recycling strategies. However, the SEM images suggest poor thermal stability of the self-assembled structures, which disappeared during the hot-pressing, as a consequence of the synergistic effect of temperature [59,60] and pressure [61]. This can be explained by a reduction of the oxygen functionalities of CDs during the hot-press step with a consequent decrease of the interlayer spacing among the dots [47]. This might break the fibrous morphology [47], although some secondary interactions among the CDs and between the CDs and the thermoset matrix are still present, conferring the thermoset with better recyclability.

Moreover, from the SEM images the presence of wide “ramifications”

is well observable in the mechanically recycled samples (Fig. 10b and c). Their formation is a clear demonstration that, during the thermal reprocessing, the imine metathesis pathway takes place among the different pieces in which the thermosets is cut. The morphology of chemically recycled XSB + CD (Fig. 10f) appears to be homogeneous with small and thin “ramifications” acting as sutures among the different parts of the sample.

The DMA analysis in multifrequency strain mode performed on mechanically recycled XSB and XSB + CD (Fig. S10) documented higher thermal stability for both recycled samples with respect to the original ones, as observable by the higher T_g and by the shift of the transition from the glassy state to the rubbery plateau towards higher temperatures. This can be ascribed to a completion of the curing of double bonds occurring during the thermal reprocessing, as also suggested by the ATR-FTIR spectra (Fig. 9c and d). In the rubbery state the behavior of recycled XSB + CD turned out to be significantly different from the one showed in Fig. 7b. Indeed, a dramatic reduction of the storage modulus can be observed for this composite at temperatures higher than T_g and the rubbery plateau is reached only at around 150 °C (vs 130 °C for XSB + CD). In agreement with our previous hypothesis, the results suggest that the CD derived fibers can act as reinforcing agent at temperature higher than T_g . However, when subjected to the hot-press reprocessing the possible additional reduction of the oxygenated groups leads to the disassembly of the fibers and the reinforcing action in the rubbery state is lost. Although the fibers are disassembled, some secondary interactions (e.g. π - π stacking) between the CDs and the surrounding matrix are still present as confirmed by better preservation of the mechanical properties after the recycling procedures (Fig. 9b).

4. Conclusions

The obtainment of a DLP 3D printable bio-based and recyclable composite thermoset by utilizing a vanillin Schiff-base resin with cellulose derived CDs was demonstrated. The morphological characterization highlighted the unexpected propension of the produced CDs dispersed in aromatic monomers to self-assemble upon UV exposure, generating microfibers. The generation, distribution and density of these microfibers in the thermoset matrix strongly depended on the employed UV curing method. In this context, with respect to the plain UV lamp, the

Fig. 10. SEM images of (a–c) mechanically and (d–f) chemically recycled XSB + CD.

layer-by-layer curing approach during DLP printing effectively promoted generation of large number of microfibers in the thermoset matrix. The shape-memory, mechanical and dynamic mechanical thermal analysis suggested a lower crosslinking density for XSB + CD compared with XSB. This is likely explained by the replacement of some of the covalent crosslinks with secondary interactions established inside the microfibers and between the microfibers and the surrounding matrix. Moreover, the stress-relaxation analysis confirmed the interaction of the CD-derived microfibers with the network, which is expressed in the hampering of the imine metathesis pathway driving the stress relaxation. Although the formed microfibers were not stable when the composites were reprocessed, the introduction of CDs in the network turns out to significantly contribute, together with the Schiff-base linkages, to the preservation of the mechanical properties of the composite when subjected to the mechanical reprocessing and chemical recycling. Indeed, while a significant decrease of the elastic modulus was detected for XSB, probably due to the non-restoration of all the damaged covalent bonds during the recycling procedures, the presence of supramolecular interactions turned out to mitigate this phenomenon leading to an almost complete preservation of the original mechanical properties. The obtained results document the synergistic effect of dynamic covalent bonds and supramolecular chemistry for the thermosets recyclability. Further work should concentrate on modification of the resin to omit the need of harmful volatile solvents to further enable printing of 3D objects with larger size and more complex architectures.

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CRediT authorship contribution statement

Anna Liguori: Conceptualization, Data curation, Formal analysis, Visualization, Validation, Funding acquisition, Investigation, Methodology, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Karla Itzel Garfias González:** Investigation, Writing – review & editing. **Minna Hakkarainen:** Conceptualization, Data curation, Funding acquisition, Supervision, Validation, Writing – review & editing.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.polymer.2023.126252>.

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